

BIO-SUSHY PFAS FREE SOLUTION WITH FOCUS ON THERMOPLASTIC BASED POWDERS FOR FOOD PACKAGING APPLICATIONS

Ivana Burzic¹, Christoph Joham¹, Antonio Munarini²

¹ Kompetenzzentrum Holz GmbH, Austria

² Ecozema, Fabbrica Pinze Schio s.r.l., Italy

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10008144

i.burzic@wood-kplus.at

Abstract: *BIO-SUSHY project aims to develop 3 PFAS-free coating materials partially or fully bio-based to be validated in 3 case studies textile, food and glass packaging. In parallel with material development covering sol-gel and thermoplastic powder coatings integration of safety and sustainability into the coating formulations using multidisciplinary approach of computational tools, predictive models and data-driven simulations is covered from an early R&D phase. The highlights from the latest results on bio-based biodegradable thermoplastic formulations using spray coating on paper substrates will be briefly presented.*

Acknowledgements: *Bio-Sushy project was Funded by the European Union GA number: 101091464. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.*